

Calculation of Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters (T_λ) in some Er^{III}-doped systems by using statistical method

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The statistical method for calculating T_λ parameters has been described. The symmetry of the Er^{III}-doped systems has been discussed on the basis of T_4/T_6 ratio. The applicability of Judd-Ofelt theory as well as statistical method used for calculation of intensity parameters (T_λ) has been established from r.m.s. deviation point of view.

Judd¹ and Ofelt² derived an equation for the oscillator strength (P) of a transition between a ground state ($f^N \psi_j$) and an excited state ($f^N \psi_j'$), of the lanthanide ion in solution given as³

$$P = \sum T_\lambda \bar{v} (f^N \psi_j \parallel U^{(\lambda)} \parallel f^N \psi_j')^2 \quad (1)$$
$$\lambda = 2, 4, 6$$

where the unit tensor operators [$U^{(\lambda)}$] connect the initial and final states via T_λ ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) parameters. The oscillator strength (P) is the probability of an electronic transitions and can be given as⁴

$$P = 4.6 \times 10^{-9} \times \epsilon_{\max} \times \Delta\bar{v}^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_{\max} is the molar extinction coefficient of the peak maximum and $\Delta\bar{v}^{1/2}$ is the half-intensity band-width, i.e. the width at $1/2 \epsilon_{\max}$. For an allowed transitions P equals to one. Since $f \leftrightarrow f$ transitions are mostly induced electric dipole transitions, the value of P is of the order of 10^{-6} , i.e. $P \ll 1$. The value of oscillator strength due to magnetic dipole and electric quadrupole is of the order of 10^{-8} and 10^{-10} respectively. The selection rules for these transitions are $\Delta J \leq 1$ and $\Delta J \leq 2$. In Judd-Ofelt parameters (T_λ), we have $\Delta J \leq \lambda$, i.e. for T_2 , T_4 and T_6 , we have $\Delta J \leq 2$, $\Delta J \leq 4$ and $\Delta J \leq 6$, respectively.

The ratio of T_4/T_6 is found to be nearly constant for the systems having the same symmetry^{5,6}. Thus the Judd-Ofelt parameters (T_λ) are the characteristic intensity parameters for the intra f^N transitions observed in the lanthanide complexes (or doped systems). Therefore, it has been found desirable to use the statistical method for computing T_λ parameters.

In the present paper, T_λ parameters for the ten Er^{III}-doped systems have been studied. In doped systems certain impurities have been added during crystal formation. This technique can be used in solution form also; here certain

metal ions (lanthanide ions) have been added to the saturated solutions of certain ligands. In our study, Er^{III} ion (in the form of Er(NO₃)₃) has been added to the saturated ethanolic solutions of ligands. The ligands includes seven amino acids (viz. L-proline, L-leucine, L-threonine, L-arginine, aspartic acid, L-cystine and β -alanine), ascorbic acid, indole and α -benzoin oxime. The saturated solutions have been prepared by dissolving ligands in 50% ethanol. A constant amount (0.05 g) of Er(NO₃)₃ has been added to 10 ml of each saturated solution. Thus Er^{III} ion is surrounded by solvent as well as ligand molecules. Solution spectrum is recorded for each Er^{III}-doped system. Calculation for oscillator strengths and Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters have been done for all the systems.

Method of calculations :

In the calculation of T_λ parameters, the statistical method known as partial and multiple regression method⁷, has been used. The purpose of the partial and multiple regression method, is to obtain a measure of the relation between two variable when the other variable is constant.

The equations for the partial and multiple regression have the form,

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_pX_p \quad (3)$$

where there are p independent variables and the regression coefficients b_1, b_2, \dots etc. are referred to as partial regression coefficients.

The observed oscillator strength may be expressed in terms of T_2, T_4 and T_6 parameters as

$$P_{\text{obs}} = T_2v [U^{(2)}]^2 + T_4v [U^{(4)}]^2 + T_6v [U^{(6)}]^2 \quad (4)$$

The values of $[U^{(2)}]^2$, $[U^{(4)}]^2$ and $[U^{(6)}]^2$ have been taken as reported by Carnall *et al.*³. The eight bands in the present Er^{III}-doped systems have been assigned the energy levels

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as ${}^2G_{9/2}$, ${}^4F_{3/2}$, ${}^4F_{5/2}$, ${}^4F_{7/2}$, ${}^2H_{11/2}$, ${}^4S_{3/2}$, ${}^4F_{9/2}$ and ${}^4I_{9/2}$. From the observed oscillator strength of the said eight bands, eight equations of the form as given in eq. (3), have been obtained. Here we have the following :

$$Y = \frac{P_{\text{obs}}}{\nu} \quad a = 0, \quad b_1 = T_2, \quad b_2 = T_4, \quad b_3 = T_6$$

$$X_1 = [U^{(2)}]^2, \quad X_2 = [U^{(4)}]^2, \quad X_3 = [U^{(6)}]^2$$

Now three steps are involved to compute the values of T_2 , T_4 and T_6 .

Step-I :

From the eight equation so obtained, the values of a_{11} , a_{12} etc. have been calculated from the relation,

$$a_{11} = \sum X_1^2, \quad a_{22} = \sum X_2^2, \quad a_{33} = \sum X_3^2, \quad a_{21} = \sum X_2 X_1, \\ a_{31} = \sum X_3 X_1, \quad a_{32} = \sum X_3 X_2$$

where,

$$\sum X_1^2 = \sum X_1^2 - \frac{(\sum X_1)^2}{N}, \quad \sum X_2^2 = \sum X_2^2 - \frac{(\sum X_2)^2}{N}$$

$$\sum X_3^2 = \sum X_3^2 - \frac{(\sum X_3)^2}{N}, \quad \sum X_2 X_1 = \sum X_2 X_1 - \left(\frac{\sum X_2 \sum X_1}{N} \right)$$

$$\sum X_3 X_1 = \sum X_3 X_1 - \left(\frac{\sum X_2 \sum X_1}{N} \right), \quad \sum X_3 X_2 = \sum X_3 X_2 - \left(\frac{\sum X_2 \sum X_1}{N} \right)$$

Here the value of $N = 8$.

Step-II :

From the values of a_{11} , a_{22} ,.... etc., the values of c_{11} , c_{12} ,....etc. have been calculated by following the instructions given below and using the matrix given in Table 1.

Table 1. Matrix for calculating c_{ij} from a_{ij}

Line	Abbreviated solutions				
1	a_{11}	a_{21}	a_{31}	1.0	0 0
2		a_{22}	a_{32}	0	1.0 0
3			a_{33}	0	0 1.0
4	a_{11}	a_{21}	a_{31}	d_{11} (1.0)	0 0
5	1.0	b_{21}	b_{31}	e_{11}	0 0
6		$a_{22.1}$	$a_{32.1}$	$d_{11.1}$	$d_{12.1}$ 0
7		1.0	$b_{32.1}$	$e_{11.1}$	$e_{12.1}$ 0
8			$a_{33.12}$	$d_{11.12}$	$d_{12.12}$ $d_{13.12}$
9			1.0	$e_{11.12}$	$e_{12.12}$ $e_{13.12}$
10				c_{11}	c_{12} c_{13}
11					c_{22} c_{23}
12					c_{33}

Instructions :

Line

1, 2, 3 ... Enter the sums of squares and products

4 ... Copy line 1

5 ... Divide each entry in line 4 by a_{11}

6 ... $a_{22.1} = a_{22} - a_{21}b_{21}$

$$a_{32.1} = a_{32} - a_{31}b_{21}$$

$$d_{11.1} = 0 - d_{11}b_{21}$$

$$d_{12.1} = 1 - 0 \times b_{21}$$

7 Divide each entry in line 6 by $a_{22.1}$

8 $a_{33.12} = a_{33} - a_{31}b_{31} - a_{32.1}b_{32.1}$

$$d_{11.12} = 0 - d_{11}b_{31} - d_{11.1}b_{32.1}$$

$$d_{12.12} = 0 - d_{12.1}b_{32.1}$$

$$d_{13.12} = 1.0$$

9 Divide each entry in line 8 by $a_{33.12}$

10, 11, 12 $c_{11} = d_{11}e_{11} + d_{11.1}e_{11.1} + d_{11.12}e_{11.12}$

$$c_{12} = d_{11.1}e_{12.1} + d_{11.12}e_{12.12}$$

$$c_{13} = d_{11.12}e_{13.12}$$

$$c_{22} = d_{12.1}e_{12.1} + d_{12.12}e_{12.12}$$

$$c_{23} = d_{12.12}e_{13.12}$$

$$c_{33} = d_{13.12}e_{13.12}$$

The values obtained for c_{11} , c_{12} etc. can be checked by the following relation :

$$c_{11} \times a_{11} + c_{12}a_{21} + c_{13}a_{31} = 1.00 \quad (5)$$

Step-III :

From the values of c_{11} , c_{12} etc., the values of b_1 (T_2), b_2 (T_4) and b_3 (T_6) can be calculated by using the relations,

$$b_1 = c_{11} \sum X_1 Y + c_{12} \sum X_2 Y + c_{13} \sum X_3 Y$$

$$b_2 = c_{12} \sum X_1 Y + c_{22} \sum X_2 Y + c_{23} \sum X_3 Y$$

$$b_3 = c_{13} \sum X_1 Y + c_{23} \sum X_2 Y + c_{33} \sum X_3 Y \quad (6)$$

Here we have

$$\sum X_1 Y + \sum X_1 Y - \left(\frac{\sum X_1 \sum Y}{N} \right), \quad \sum X_2 Y = \sum X_2 Y - \left(\frac{\sum X_2 \sum Y}{N} \right)$$

$$\sum X_3 Y = \sum X_3 Y - \left(\frac{\sum X_3 \sum Y}{N} \right)$$

Here $N = 8$.

In the present calculation, the values of c_{11} c_{12} ... etc. have been computed and are given as follows :

$$c_{11} = 3.74 \quad c_{12} = -2.74 \quad c_{13} = 2.044 \\ c_{22} = 5.4485 \quad c_{33} = 4.748 \quad c_{23} = -2.183$$

From the values of c_{11} , c_{12} ... etc. given here, the T_λ parameters can be computed for any complex (or doped system) where only the said eight bands are considered. If

Table 2. Computed values of oscillator strengths observed in Er^{III}-doped systems

Compd. →	Er ^{III} + pro	Er ^{III} + leu	Er ^{III} + thr	Er ^{III} + arg	Er ^{III} + asp	Er ^{III} + cys	Er ^{III} + ala	Er ^{III} + asc	Er ^{III} + ind	Er ^{III} + bzo
	$P_{\text{obs}} \times 10^6 /$ $(P_{\text{cal}} \times 10^6)$									
² G _{9/2}	1.708 (0.735)	0.946 (0.3915)	0.828 (0.5021)	0.966 (0.4348)	2.168 (0.584)	1.409 (0.753)	1.872 (0.9027)	1.2416 (1.324)	0.972 (0.4019)	1.428 (0.5158)
⁴ F _{3/2}	1.231 (0.363)	0.591 (0.0976)	0.673 (0.2481)	0.640 (0.2118)	1.629 (0.2795)	1.055 (0.381)	1.445 (0.4604)	1.0051 (0.668)	0.709 (0.1995)	0.903 (0.2496)
⁴ F _{5/2}	1.256 (0.6372)	1.248 (0.3375)	1.242 (0.4360)	1.212 (0.3714)	2.313 (0.4901)	1.576 (0.667)	2.208 (0.8054)	1.3240 (1.169)	1.458 (0.3498)	1.472 (0.4376)
⁴ F _{7/2}	3.075 (1.807)	1.458 (0.8701)	1.725 (1.2354)	1.616 (1.0961)	2.819 (1.5375)	2.710 (1.754)	3.371 (2.0877)	2.3063 (3.076)	1.622 (0.9788)	1.872 (1.3214)
² H _{11/2}	5.888 (4.893)	4.140 (3.5373)	3.942 (3.4248)	3.548 (2.9138)	5.913 (4.5316)	4.375 (3.586)	5.520 (4.3177)	3.3120 (3.643)	3.942 (3.217)	5.092 (4.0640)
⁴ S _{3/2}	2.093 (0.529)	1.265 (0.2808)	1.153 (0.3619)	1.458 (0.3078)	2.139 (0.4085)	1.576 (0.554)	2.513 (0.6701)	1.2316 (0.974)	1.182 (0.2910)	2.562 (0.3647)
⁴ F _{9/2}	2.039 (1.355)	1.314 (0.7656)	1.380 (0.9379)	1.478 (0.9049)	2.648 (1.4424)	1.603 (1.043)	2.208 (1.1760)	1.3403 (1.851)	1.340 (0.7131)	2.050 (1.1462)
⁴ I _{9/2}	0.985 (0.1433)	0.427 (0.1664)	0.427 (0.1009)	0.476 (0.1162)	1.040 (0.2234)	0.683 (0.176)	0.966 (0.3010)	0.6140 (0.0828)	0.509 (0.0700)	0.673 (0.1618)
	$\sigma \pm 1.0184$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 0.6544$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 0.544$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 0.673$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 1.428$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 0.7793$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 1.218$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 0.4265$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 0.7186$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$\sigma \pm 1.095$ $\times 10^{-6}$

σ = r.m.s. deviation.

some other bands are considered, then fresh calculations for c_{11} , c_{12} etc. will have to be performed⁷.

Results and Discussion

The intensities of the observed bands have been given in terms of oscillator strengths. The observed values of oscillator strength have been compared with those of the calculated ones (using Judd-Ofelt equation). The r.m.s. deviation varies within the range of 0.4265×10^{-6} to 1.428×10^{-6} , and are reported in Tables 2. The small deviation for the calculated and observed (P_{obs}) values suggests the validity of Judd-Ofelt equation for $f \leftrightarrow f$ transitions for the systems under study.

The Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters (T_2 , T_4 and T_6) and the ratio T_4/T_6 and T_4/T_2 are reported in Table 3. The values of all the three T_λ parameters show substantial variation. It is well known that T_2 parameter shows high sensitivity towards coordination changes while T_4 and T_6 have been found to exhibit more sensitivity towards symmetry changes^{7,8}. The ratio T_4/T_6 varies between (-) 0.015 and 0.9182 and the ratio T_4/T_2 varies from (-) 0.0085 to 0.3505. It suggests that symmetry changes are more prominent than coordination changes.

The values of T_λ parameters for Er^{III}-doped systems shows a general sequence of $T_2 > T_6 > T_4$ (except in ascorbic acid). T_2 parameter, which is covalency denoting

parameter, is expected to increase due to lanthanide contraction as reduction in size of cation favors covalent bonding. The values of T_4 parameter for all the systems reduced to lower values. The β -alanine, we have observed the negative value for T_4 , which is in accordance with the results as reported by Carnall *et al.*³.

The transition $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^2H_{11/2}$ of Er^{III} has been considered 'Hypersensitive' while other $4f \leftrightarrow 4f$ transitions are regarded only marginally sensitive or almost insensitive^{5,6,9}. Recently, Devlin *et al.*¹⁰ have made a detailed study of electric dipole intensity parameters and oscillator strengths of multiplet electronic transitions of Nd^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes with structurally related ligands. These workers found that $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$, $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4S_{3/2}$ transitions of Er^{III} which do not follow selection rules, $\Delta L \leq 2$, $\Delta J \leq 2$ and $\Delta S = 0$, yet show substantially high sensitivity towards even minor coordination changes occurring around Er^{III}. Misra *et al.*⁸ also noted the sensitivity of certain transitions in Pr^{III} and Nd^{III}, and they named such transitions as 'ligand mediated pseudo-hypersensitivity'. In certain systems (viz. L-proline, aspartic acid and L-cystine, β -alanine and ascorbic acid) we also observed ligand-mediated pseudo-hypersensitivity for $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$ and $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4S_{3/2}$ transitions.

It is a well known fact that T_2 parameter shows high sensitivity towards coordination changes while T_4 and T_6 exhibit more sensitivity towards symmetry changes. Thus the ratio T_4/T_6 (Judd-Ofelt parameter ratio) may be used for determining the change in symmetry around lanthanide ion.

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In the same way T_4/T_2 ratio may be used for knowing the variation in coordination number around lanthanide ion in doped systems or in complexes. However, these parameters (T_4/T_6 and T_4/T_2) do not give any information regarding absolute value of symmetry or coordination number.

As per the values of T_4/T_6 and T_4/T_2 , Er^{III} -doped systems may be classified arbitrarily into the following groups :

	T_4/T_6 value	T_4/T_2 value	Ligand
Group A	0.0770 – 0.3655	0.0450 – 0.1253	cys, asc, ind
Group B	0.4197 – 0.9182	0.1540 – 0.3505	pro, leu, thr, arg, asp, bzo

Each group represents almost identical symmetry or coordination number around Er^{III} ion in solution. Since the negative values of Judd-Ofelt parameters are insignificant, hence for classification purpose, only positive values of T_4/T_6 and T_4/T_2 are used. The T_2 , T_4 and T_6 values are the functions of the refractive index of the medium, the radial wave functions of the initial and final states of the perturbation mechanism parameters. In general, T_λ is considered as an empirical parameter and calculated from the experimental intensities.

Although the Judd-Ofelt theory is not able to elucidate the nature of T_λ , it has proved to be a very useful working tool to make it possible to discuss the intensities of numerous absorption bands using only three parameters.

Carnall *et al.*³, in solution spectral studies, have used τ_λ , independent of multiplicity of the ground state,

$$\tau_\lambda = T_\lambda (2J + 1) \quad (7)$$

where τ_λ is Judd-Ofelt intensity parameter.

Axe¹¹, while studying crystals, has used Ω_λ , independent of the refraction factor,

$$\Omega_\lambda = \frac{\tau_\lambda}{\chi [8\pi^2 mc/3h]} \quad (8)$$

where, χ is Lorenz field correction for refractivity of the sample medium.

Table 3. Computed values of T_λ parameters

Sl. no.	$T_2 \times 10^{10}$	$T_4 \times 10^{10}$	$T_6 \times 10^{10}$	T_4/T_6	T_4/T_2	Er^{III} systems
1.	3.0090	0.5370	1.2794	0.4197	0.1784	L-Proline
2.	2.2320	0.3438	0.6776	0.5073	0.1540	L-Leucine
3.	2.1060	0.3804	0.8732	0.4356	0.1806	L-Threonine
4.	1.7120	0.4546	0.7456	0.6097	0.2655	Arginine
5.	2.5774	0.9034	0.9838	0.9182	0.3505	Aspartic acid
6.	2.3160	0.1043	1.3420	0.9770	0.0450	L-Cystine
7.	2.8520	(-0.0244)	1.6168	(-0.0150)	(-0.0085)	β -Alanine
8.	2.1738	0.2073	2.3517	0.0881	0.0953	Ascorbic acid
9.	2.0474	0.2567	0.7022	0.3655	0.1253	Indole
10.	2.4080	0.6444	0.7334	0.8785	0.2676	α -Benzoin oxime

The parameter T_2 is predicted to be the most sensitive to

covalency⁵. Hence the order of covalencies in Er^{III} -doped systems with respect to T_2 values are : pro > ala > asp > bzo > cys > leu > asc > thr > ind > arg. Thus proline exhibits strongest metal-ligand interactions, leading to strongest covalent character in doped system.

In the present study lanthanide (erbium)-doped systems are preferably selected against synthesis of various lanthanide ion complexes. This is due to the well known fact that lanthanide ion complexes are generally kinetically and thermodynamically less stable as compared to transition metal ion complexes.

Experimental

Standard grade chemicals $\text{Er}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (99.9%) (Aldrich), amino acids (L-proline, L-leucine, L-threonine, arginine, aspartic acid, L-cystine and β -alanine), ascorbic acid, indole and α -benzoin oxime (SD's fine chem.) and ethanol (99.5%) were used.

The various saturated solutions of ligands were prepared at room temp. (35°) in 50% ethanol. To each saturated ligand solution (10 ml), $\text{Er}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, (99.9%; 0.05 g) was added, and after shaking for 10 min, spectrum of each solution was taken. The electronic spectra of these solutions are taken in the range of 400–820 nm by using a Systronics-106 spectrophotometer.

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